

Personality Traits as Predictors of Adolescents' Susceptibility to Peer Pressure in Secondary Schools in Anambra State

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between the five levels of personality traits and adolescents' susceptibility to peer pressure in secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Seven research questions and seven hypotheses guided the study. The design of the study was correlational research design. The population comprised 55,696 adolescents in senior secondary schools in Anambra State. A sample size of 1,000 senior secondary school students was selected through proportionate stratified and convenience sampling techniques. The research instrument that was used in the study is a validated and reliable questionnaire. Pearson's coefficient of determination was used to answer the research questions, Regression statistics were used to test hypotheses 1-6 while Fisher-z statistics was used to test hypothesis 7. The hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between the Big-5 personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents; that there is a significant relationship between neuroticism and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents; that there is a significant relationship between conscientiousness and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents; that there is a significant relationship between openness and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents; that there is a significant relationship between extraversion and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents; and that there is a significant relationship between agreeableness and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents. The study also found that there is a significant moderating impact of sex in the relationship between personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents. Based on these findings, it was recommended amongst others, that educational programmes should be developed for teenagers that enhance self-awareness of personality traits and how they can influence susceptibility to peer pressure.

Keywords: Personality Traits; Adolescents; Peer Pressure; Secondary Schools; Big-5

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Introduction

Adolescence is the period of development that begins at puberty and ends at early adulthood or emerging adulthood; the typical age range is from 10 to 18 years, and this stage of development has some predictable milestones. During adolescence, children gain 50% of their adult body weight, experience puberty become capable of reproducing, and experience an astounding transformation in their brains. All of these changes occur in the context of rapidly expanding social spheres. These changes can be categorized into physical, cognitive, and psychosocial.

Physical changes include the onset of puberty, hormonal changes, sexual maturation and growth spurt. Cognitive changes include improvements in complex and abstract thought, the formal stage as well as the development that happens at different rates in distinct parts of the brain, which increases adolescents' propensity for risky behaviour because an increase in sensation-seeking and reward motivation precedes an increase in cognitive control. Within the psychosocial domain, changes in relationships include those with parents, peers, and romantic partners.

Growing into adolescence, children spend more and more time with peers without parent or adult supervision and peer groups become the adolescents' main reference group. Erik Erikson in his theory of psycho-social development, refers to this development stage as searching for identity. To achieve identity, teenagers strive to be independent of parental control, influences, and protection. However, this brings a sense of uncertainty and conflicts with adult values, which pushes them to seek peer support and acceptance as a kind of assurance for their identity. Peers refer to individuals who are similar in age, social status, or other shared characteristics and who belong to the same social group or community. When adolescents have more and closer interactions with peers, they are, at the same time, more subject to peer pressure and are more likely to be exposed to the problematic behaviour of their peers.

The concept of peer pressure in the adolescence period is associated with the process of interaction between peers, in which children and young people accept the characteristics of those peers for whom they feel sympathy. Peer pressure is a multidimensional construct because adolescents perceive it in different areas of their lives: participation in family activities, school activities, activities with peers, conforming to peer norms and risk behaviours. They are afraid

of being rejected by peers and, hence, must conform to peer interests. Adolescents respond to peer pressure by accepting it and conforming to their peer's norms, expectations or demands or ignoring it, and by confronting it with a counter-influence.

Peers affect adolescents' decisions to engage (or not engage) in risky behaviours (Blakemore & Mills, 2014). Social acceptance becomes central to much of adolescent behaviour, perhaps because it is a developmentally sensitive period in which youths are highly attuned to picking up on and responding to social cues from their social environments. Thus, to the degree that social conformity is perceived as central to popularity among peers, early and middle adolescents are especially vulnerable to peer pressure as they strive toward peer approval and acceptance.

As relationships with peers become increasingly salient during adolescence, the urge to do what peers direct one to do grows stronger in many spheres of the adolescent's life. It is not surprising, thus, that peer pressure is a common theme in adolescent development. Peers often exert pressure by threatening with negative emotions as a reaction to mockery, rejection or non-acceptance. Anxiety provoked by the fear of relationship loss can be a powerful encouragement for adolescents to change their behaviour and adjust to peer expectations. Blakemore and Mills (2014) stated that one of the strongest predictors of adolescent delinquency is the delinquency level of close friends. Peers also seem to contribute to health-compromising behaviours such as drug use or risky sexual activities.

Peer pressure appears to be a major source of social ills among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State, Nigeria. Observation by the researcher has shown that these individuals are always seen together, and when they are together, they often indulge in a series of social vices like drug abuse, substance use, cybercrimes, prostitution and other social vices. These days, they converge more in hotels than in their homes and schools. They are seen roaming the streets driving different fleets of porch cars drinking different sorts of alcohol mixed with substances. When these individuals leave their homes for school, they become something else when they meet with their friends. Most times, these individuals may be from very good homes with good upbringings. But on getting to the schools and mixing with friends, they start exhibiting different sorts of social misdemeanours due to their interaction with their peers. However, such influence may be determined by the level of the individuals' peer pressure. After all, not all individuals from good homes become deviant when they leave their

homes. Some still maintain their family and religious values, no matter who they interact with. According to Chan and Chan (2011), when nondeviant and deviant adolescents interact, the direction of influence is affected by the degree of peer pressure.

Despite all that we have learned about the relevance and impact of peer pressure, however, we still know virtually nothing about which adolescents are most likely to be particularly susceptible to these pressures. Existing research has focused almost entirely upon assessing either broad developmental trends, or the extent to which individuals are exposed to peer pressure, but not how individual adolescents handle this pressure. Research to date thus leaves unaddressed the developmentally critical question about the degree to which individual adolescents differ in their levels of peer pressure. Because of this knowledge gap, the researcher feels the need to undertake a study on the personality traits of adolescents who are susceptible to peer pressure.

Personality can be defined as psychological qualities that contribute to an individual's enduring and distinctive patterns of feeling, thinking, and behaving (Oyibo & Vassileva, 2017). The Big Five is a comprehensive and widely accepted model of personality, with wide application in different domains and across cultures. According to Oyibo and Vassileva (2017), the Big Five personality traits influence the responsiveness of individuals to various persuasive strategies. They are classified into agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, extraversion and openness.

Neuroticism is a traits that is associated with emotional instability, anxiety, insecurity and fear. Oyibo and Vassileva (2019) stated that individuals who are high in Neuroticism are more likely to be susceptible to peer pressure than individuals who are low in Neuroticism. A plausible explanation for this assertion is that those high on neuroticism feel more insecure and anxious in uncertain situations and have less autonomy than those low on neuroticism. Thus, they are more prone to peer pressure in new situations and the face of uncertainties. These positions confirm the social psychology theory on neuroticism and replicate existing findings in the health and social media domains.

Conscientiousness is a traits associated with being self-disciplined, well-organized, thoughtful, and goal-oriented. Those high in this traits tend to be perfectionists in their jobs and great achievers of their aspirations and goals. Oyibo and Vassileva (2019) stated that individuals who are low in conscientiousness are more likely to be susceptible to peer pressure than

individuals who are high in Conscientiousness; there may be possible explanation for this assertion First, given that individuals high in conscientiousness are more thoughtful than those low in conscientiousness, it is more likely that, during an uncertain situation, the former will spend more time in thinking about the situation and finding a possible solution to it rather than resorting to learning, imitating or copying others as a way of social proof or validation. Second, given that individuals high in conscientiousness are more goal-oriented than those low in conscientiousness, the former is more likely to be focused on achieving their personal goals than engaging in social interactions—be it online or offline. This characteristic behaviour of relying on others may make them more susceptible to pressure.

Openness is a traits associated with creativity and novelty. Openness, on the other hand, is a traits that characterizes people who are intellectually curious, imaginative and creative. Individuals who are high in this traits tend to be adventurous and open to new ideas and experiences. Oyibo and Vassileva (2019) stated that individuals who are low in Openness are more likely to be susceptible to peer pressure than individuals who are high in Openness. This can be attributed to the theory that states that individuals who are low in openness are less imaginative and innovative as compared to individuals who are high in openness. Individuals low in openness are more of imitators, while HO individuals are more of initiators. Thus, while individuals who are high in openness tend to do more innovative things than go with the norm or follow the crowd, the opposite is the case for those low in openness. DeYoung (2012) found that openness (together with Extraversion) negatively correlates with conformity to societal or group norms. In other words, the more open a person is, the less conforming to social norms he or she tends to be. Similarly, Oyibo and Vassileva (2017), in prior studies, found that Openness negatively influences Consensus.

Extraversion reflects individual differences in sociability and social ascendancy. Extraversion is a traits that characterizes people who possess the tendency to socialize and interact with others. Those high in this traits tend to be warm, assertive, seek fun and love positive feelings. They are most likely to be influenced by their peers. However, this assertion is yet to be verified as studies seem to be scarce on the influence of extraversion personality on peer pressure. Agreeableness is a traits that characterizes people who are friendly, sympathetic and altruistic. Those high in this traits tend to be approachable, compassionate, modest, non-confrontational and less competitive. This category of people may be difficult to influence by

their peers. The above personality traits will be explored in terms of their relationship with adolescents' peer pressure.

Given the above, the focus of this study is on the relationship that exists between the five levels of personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised and answered to guide the study:

1. What is the relationship between the Big-5 personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State?
2. What is the relationship between neuroticism personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State?
3. What is the relationship between conscientiousness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State?
4. What is the relationship between openness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State?
5. What is the relationship between extraversion personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State?
6. What is the relationship between agreeableness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State?
7. What is the moderating impact of sex in the relationship between personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between the Big-5 personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State
2. There is no significant relationship between neuroticism personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State.
3. There is no significant relationship between conscientiousness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State.

4. There is no significant relationship between openness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State.
5. There is no significant relationship between extraversion personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State.
6. There is no significant relationship between agreeableness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State.
7. There is no significant moderating impact of sex in the relationship between personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State.

Methods

This study employed a correlational research design. The population of this study comprised 55,696 adolescents in senior secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample size comprised 1,000 senior secondary school students. The sampling technique that was used for the study is the proportionate stratified sampling technique. A proportionate stratified sampling technique is a probability sampling method in which different strata in a population are identified and in which the number of elements drawn from each stratum is proportionate to the relative number of elements in each stratum. The reason for this choice of sampling technique was that all the local government areas that were used in the study did not have an equal number of senior secondary school students. Hence, there was the need to represent the population of students in each Local Government Area. In doing this, the researcher estimated the percentage of the sample size concerning the overall population size, which resulted in 1.795%. In other words, 1.795% of the total number of students in each local government area will be selected.

The research instrument that was used in the study is a questionnaire. The questionnaire contains two sections: Section A requests respondents to supply their bio-data details while Section B contains two scales viz: Personality Traits Rating Scale and Adolescent Peer Pressure Rating Scale. The Personality Traits Rating Scale was adapted from the Big Five Inventory (BFI), developed by Golberg (1993). The Big Five Inventory (BFI) is a self-report scale that is designed to measure the Big Five personality traits (extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness). It contains 41 items, which were reduced to 26 after validation. The items were measured on a 4-point scale, ranging from 1 for strongly

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disagree to 4 for strongly agree. In adapting the instrument, some items in the original instrument were reworded to reflect the language ability of the students in the location of study. Some items that appeared complex to the students were simplified while others were removed during validation. The Adolescents' Peer Pressure Rating Scale was adapted from Palani and Mani's Perceived Peer Pressure Scale (2016). There are 30 items on the scale in all but this was reduced to 21 (10 items measuring Yielding to Peer Pressure, 9 items measuring Resistance to Peer Pressure, and 2 items measuring peer encouragement). The scale of the items ranged from 1 for strongly disagree to 4 for strongly agree on a 4-point scale. In adapting the instrument, some items in the original instrument were reworded to reflect the language ability of the students in the location of study. Some items that appeared complex to the students were simplified while others were removed during validation.

The instrument has a face, content and construct validities. The instrument was given to experts in the Department of Guidance and Counselling, as well as one psychometrician. The reason for using experts in the validation was to gain their insight as to appropriate matching of the items to the domains and content areas arrangement and appropriateness of the item options (Jessa, et al., 2023). The experts made some inputs and suggestions which were reflected in the final instrument. After the face validity, the researcher administered 100 copies of the instrument to senior secondary school students in Asaba, which is outside the study area. The data was subjected to factor analysis. The content and construct validity of the instrument was estimated by using factor analysis and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with extraction method. It yielded the following Total Cumulative Variances Extraversion Personality Scale = 52.06%; Neuroticism Personality Scale = 61.31%; Openness Personality Scale = 77.03%; Agreeableness Personality Scale = 61.54%; Conscientiousness Personality Scale = 61.82%; and Adolescents' Peer pressure = 77.69%. These values imply that the instruments have content validity. The rotated factor loading/component matrix accounted for the construct validity while the total cumulative variance accounted for the content validity of the instrument. It yielded the following range of scores: Extraversion Personality Scale = 0.54-0.79; Neuroticism Personality Scale = 0.60-0.92; Openness Personality Scale = 0.81-0.96; Agreeableness Personality Scale = 0.68-0.82; Conscientiousness Personality Scale = 0.54-0.88; and Adolescents' Peer pressure = 0.52-0.91. These values imply that the instruments have construct validity. Cronbach alpha method was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. The instrument was

administered to 100 respondents in Asaba. The responses were subjected to the use of the Cronbach alpha method. The coefficients obtained include Extraversion Personality Scale = 0.69; Neuroticism Personality Scale = 0.70; Openness Personality Scale = 0.72; Agreeableness Personality Scale = 0.0.72; Conscientiousness Personality Scale = 0.60; and Adolescents' Peer pressure = 0.80. These values imply that the instruments are reliable.

The research instrument was administered by the researchers with the help of five research assistants who were trained on the purpose of the study and how to administer the instrument. Before administration, the researcher sought and obtained permission from the principals of the various schools. Adequate explanation was given to the respondents before administration. This was to avoid misinterpretation and to ensure a proper understanding of the instrument. Respondents were encouraged to respond sincerely to the questionnaire as their responses would be kept in utmost confidentiality since the instrument is meant for academic research purposes. Copies of the questionnaire were retrieved immediately the same day after completion. Regression statistics were used to test hypotheses 1-6 while the Fisher-z statistics were used to test hypothesis 7. The hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between the Big-5 personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State?

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the Big-5 personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State

Table 1: Multiple regression analysis of the relationship between the Big-5 personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	P
Regression	3512.437	5	702.487		
Residual	28085.019	994	28.255	24.863	.000 ^b
Total	31597.456	999			

Variables in Equation					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficient	Standardised Coefficient	t	p	
	B	Beta			
				Error	
Constant	48.673		20.344	.000	
Neuroticism Personality	-.240	-.086	-2.843	.005	
Conscientiousness Personality	.417	.151	4.752	.000	
Openness Personality	.403	.150	4.831	.000	
Extraversion Personality	.242	.069	2.279	.023	
Agreeableness Personality	.313	.133	4.264	.000	

$\alpha = 0.05$; $R = 0.33$; $R^2 = 0.11$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.11$

a. Dependent Variable: Peer Pressure

b. Predictors (Constant): Neuroticism; Conscientiousness; Openness; Extraversion; Agreeableness Personalities

Table 4.1 shows a multiple regression analysis, which was run to determine the relationship between the Big-5 personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. Results showed that the model (combination of all the predictors) as a whole can predict peer pressure. The model as a whole explains 11% of the variance in peer pressure, $R^2 = 0.11$, $F(5, 994) = 24.86$, $p < 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a significant relationship between the Big-5 personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. Conscientiousness personality makes the strongest unique contribution in explaining peer pressure among secondary school adolescents (with a Beta value of 0.15) while extraversion

personality makes less of a contribution (with a Beta value of 0.07). All the predictors (neuroticism, conscientiousness, openness, extraversion and agreeableness personality) make a statistically significant unique contribution to the equation with a P-value of 0.005, 0.000, 0.000, 0.023 and 0.000 respectively, which are less than 0.05 level of significance. The unstandardized coefficient for predicting peer pressure from neuroticism personality is -0.24, conscientiousness personality is 0.42, openness personality is 0.40, Extraversion Personality is 0.24 and agreeableness personality is 0.31. The standardized coefficient (Beta) includes neuroticism personality = -0.09, $t = -2.84$; conscientiousness personality = 0.15, $t = 4.75$; openness personality = 0.15, $t = 4.83$; extraversion personality = 0.07, $t = 2.28$; and agreeableness personality = 0.13, $t = 4.26$.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between neuroticism personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State?

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between neuroticism personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State

Table 2: Regression analysis of the relationship between neuroticism personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	P
Regression	342.272	1	342.272		
Residual	31255.184	998	31.318	10.929	.001 ^b
Total	31597.456	999			

Variables in Equation

Model	Unstandardized		Standardised	t	p
	Coefficient		Coefficient		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	69.851	1.294		53.966	.000
Neuroticism Personality	-.290	.088	-.104	-3.306	.001

$\alpha = 0.05$; $R = 0.10$; $R^2 = 0.01$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.01$

- a. **Dependent Variable:** Peer pressure
- b. **Predictors (Constant):** Neuroticism personality

Table 2 shows a regression analysis, which was run to determine the relationship between neuroticism personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. Results showed that neuroticism personality traits can predict peer pressure. It explains 1% to the variance in peer pressure, $R^2 = 0.01$, $F(1, 999) = 10.93$, $p < 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a significant relationship between neuroticism personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. The unstandardized coefficient for predicting peer pressure from neuroticism personality is -0.29 while the standardized coefficient (Beta) = -0.10, $t = -3.31$.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between conscientiousness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State?

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between conscientiousness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State

Table 3: Regression analysis of the relationship between conscientiousness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	P
Regression	1725.485	1	1725.485		
Residual	29871.971	998	29.932	57.647	.000 ^b
Total	31597.456	999			

Model	Variables in Equation		t	p
	Unstandardized	Standardised		
	Coefficient	Coefficient		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
Constant	56.814	1.172		48.491 .000
Conscientiousness Personality	.646	.085	.234	7.593 .000

$\alpha = 0.05$; $R = 0.23$; $R^2 = 0.06$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.05$

- a. **Dependent Variable:** Peer pressure
- b. **Predictors (Constant):** Conscientiousness personality

Table 3 shows a regression analysis, which was run to determine the relationship between conscientiousness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school

Adolescents in Anambra State. Results showed that conscientiousness personality traits can predict peer pressure. It explains 6% of the variance in peer pressure, $R^2 = 0.06$, $F(1, 999) = 57.65$, $p < 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a significant relationship between conscientiousness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. The unstandardized coefficient for predicting peer pressure from conscientiousness personality is 0.65 while the standardized coefficient (Beta) = 0.23, $t = 7.59$.

Research Question 4: What is the relationship between openness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State?

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between openness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State

Table 4: Regression analysis of the relationship between openness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	P
Regression	1476.970	1	1476.970		
Residual	30120.486	998	30.181	48.937	.000 ^b
Total	31597.456	999			

Variables in Equation

Model	Unstandardized		Standardised	t	p
	Coefficient		Coefficient		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	56.452	1.321		42.741	.000
Openness Personality	.579	.083	.216	6.996	.000

$\alpha = 0.05$; $R = 0.22$; $R^2 = 0.05$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.05$

- a. **Dependent Variable:** Peer pressure
- b. **Predictors (Constant):** Openness personality

Table 4 shows a regression analysis, which was run to determine the relationship between openness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. Results showed that openness personality traits can predict peer

pressure. It explains 1% of the variance in peer pressure, $R^2 = 0.06$, $F(1, 999) = 57.65$, $p < 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a significant relationship between openness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. The unstandardized coefficient for predicting peer pressure from openness personality is 0.58 while the standardized coefficient (Beta) = 0.22, $t = 7.00$.

Research Question 5: What is the relationship between extraversion personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State?

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant relationship between extraversion personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State

Table 5: Regression analysis of the relationship between extraversion personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	P
Regression	326.939	1	326.939		
Residual	31270.517	998	31.333	10.434	.001 ^b
Total	31597.456	999			

Variables in Equation

Model	Unstandardized		Standardised	t	p
	Coefficient		Coefficient		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	61.436	1.305		47.083	.000
Extraversion Personality	.354	.110	.102	3.230	.001

$\alpha = 0.05$; $R = 0.10$; $R^2 = 0.01$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.01$

- a. **Dependent Variable:** Peer Pressure
- b. **Predictors (Constant):** Extraversion personality

Table 5 shows a regression analysis, which was run to determine the relationship between extraversion personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. Results showed that extraversion personality traits can predict peer pressure. It explains 1% to the variance in peer pressure, $R^2 = 0.01$, $F(1, 999) = 10.43$, $p <$

0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a significant relationship between extraversion personality and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. The unstandardized coefficient for predicting peer pressure from extraversion personality is 0.35 while the standardized coefficient (Beta) = 0.10, $t = 3.23$.

Research Question 6: What is the relationship between agreeableness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State?

Hypothesis 6: There is no significant relationship between agreeableness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State

Table 6: Regression analysis of the relationship between agreeableness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State

Model	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	P
Regression	1338.018	1	1338.018		
Residual	30259.438	998	30.320	44.130	.000 ^b
Total	31597.456	999			

Variables in Equation

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardised Coefficient	t	p
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	57.033	1.303		43.766	.000
Agreeableness Personality	.485	.073	.206	6.643	.000

$\alpha = 0.05$; $R = 0.21$; $R^2 = 0.04$; Adjusted $R^2 = 0.04$

- a. **Dependent Variable:** Peer Pressure
- b. **Predictors (Constant):** Agreeableness personality

Table 6 shows a regression analysis, which was run to determine the relationship between agreeableness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. Results showed that agreeableness personality traits can predict peer pressure. It explains 4% of the variance in peer pressure, $R^2 = 0.04$, $F(1, 999) = 44.13$, $p < 0.05$ level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a

significant relationship between agreeableness personality and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. The unstandardized coefficient for predicting peer pressure from agreeableness personality is 0.49 while the standardized coefficient (Beta) = 0.21, $t = 6.64$.

Research Question 7: What is the moderating impact of sex in the relationship between personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State?

Hypothesis 7: There is no significant moderating impact of sex in the relationship between personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State

Table 7: Multiple correlation and Fisher’s Z statistics of the moderating impact of sex in the relationship between personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State

Sex	Variables	<i>n</i>	<i>R</i>	Fisher-z	Remark
Male	Neuroticism Personality	770	0.09	2.30	Significant
	Conscientiousness Personality				
	Openness Personality				
	Extraversion Personality				
	Agreeableness Personality				
Female	Peer Pressure	230	0.31		
	Neuroticism Personality				
	Conscientiousness Personality				
	Openness Personality				
	Extraversion Personality				
	Agreeableness Personality				
	Peer Pressure				

Table 7 showed a multiple correlation and Fisher’s Z statistics which were used to determine the moderating impact of sex in the relationship between personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. The result revealed a significant moderating impact, ($R [m] = 0.09$; $R [f] = 0.31$; $Z = 2.30$). Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, which means that there is a

significant moderating impact of sex in the relationship between personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State.

Discussion

The first finding showed that there is a significant relationship between the Big-5 personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. This finding suggests a fascinating link between personality traits and how susceptible senior secondary school adolescents are to peer pressure. This finding is not surprising. This is because outgoing and social teens (high extroversion) might be more easily swayed by their peers' desires for excitement or social validation. They may be more likely to give in to peer pressure to participate in risky or attention-seeking behaviours. Teens who are cooperative and eager to please others (high agreeableness) might find it difficult to say no to their friends, even if they are uncomfortable with the situation. Organized and goal-oriented teens (high conscientiousness) are likely to be more resistant to peer pressure that goes against their values or goals. They may be better at planning and sticking to their own decisions. Emotionally sensitive teens (high neuroticism) might be more vulnerable to peer pressure as a way to cope with social anxiety or fear of rejection. Teens who are curious and enjoy new experiences (high openness) might be more susceptible to peer pressure that involves trying new things, even if those things are risky.

The above finding agrees with the results of other previous studies. For instance, Studies by McCrae and John (1992) establish the Big Five as a robust framework for understanding personality. Subsequent research by Liu et al. (2021) supports the link between extroversion and peer pressure. Their findings suggest that adolescents high in extroversion are more likely to engage in risky behaviours (potentially due to a desire for social excitement) when influenced by peers. This aligns with the idea that extroverts crave social stimulation and may struggle to resist peer influence in pursuit of that validation. Similarly, research by Cote et al. (2020) aligns with the idea that agreeableness can be a vulnerability factor. Their study suggests that teenagers high in agreeableness prioritize social harmony and might struggle to assert themselves against peer pressure, even when they disapprove.

A study by Cacioppo and Hawkley (2020) suggests a connection between neuroticism and social anxiety. This aligns with the concept that adolescents high in neuroticism, and prone to fear of rejection, might be more susceptible to peer pressure for fear of social exclusion. Openness to experience, another Big Five trait, presents a more nuanced picture. While some research, like Chen et al. (2011), suggests a link between openness and susceptibility to peer pressure, particularly regarding trying new things, it is important to distinguish between positive and negative experiences. Openness does not necessarily equate to a willingness to engage in risky behaviours. Conscientiousness, characterized by organization and goal-oriented behaviour, might appear to offer protection against peer pressure. However, the situation plays a role. As research by Donahue et al. (2015) suggests, highly conscientious teens might still succumb to peer pressure if it aligns with their existing goals. For example, a conscientious student might agree to study with friends even if it is not their preferred study method.

The second finding revealed that there is a significant relationship between neuroticism personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. This finding implies that neuroticism, characterized by emotional sensitivity, anxiety, and a tendency to experience negative emotions, can be linked to susceptibility to peer pressure among senior secondary school adolescents. This relationship is complex and may be influenced by various factors. For instance, Neurotic adolescents often experience social anxiety, making them hypersensitive to social cues and fearing rejection. Peer pressure can be seen as a way to gain acceptance and avoid social exclusion, a significant concern for this age group. Studies by Cacioppo and Hawkley (2020) suggest a connection between neuroticism and social anxiety. This aligns with the concept that adolescents high in neuroticism, and prone to fear of rejection, might be more susceptible to peer pressure for fear of social exclusion. Peer pressure can be a source of stress and anxiety. Conforming might be seen as a way to alleviate these negative emotions in the short term, even if it goes against their better judgment.

The above finding agrees with the results of previous studies. For instance, studies like one by Cacioppo and Hawkley (2020) stated that adolescents high in neuroticism often experience social anxieties, making them more attuned to social cues and fearful of rejection. Peer pressure can be perceived as a way to gain acceptance and avoid ostracism, a significant concern for this age group. Conforming to the group, even if it involves engaging in undesirable

activities, might be seen as a way to manage their anxiety in the short term. A study by Kotov et al. (2010) suggests that individuals high in neuroticism struggle with managing negative emotions effectively. Peer pressure can be a source of stress and anxiety. Conforming to the group's demands might be seen as a quick way to alleviate these negative emotions, even if it goes against their values or long-term goals.

The third finding showed that there is a significant relationship between conscientiousness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. This finding implies that conscientiousness, characterized by organization, goal-oriented behaviour, and self-control, presents a fascinating twist in the story of peer pressure among senior secondary school adolescents. On the surface, it seems logical that conscientious teens, with their focus on plans and goals, would be less susceptible to peer pressure. However, it is important to consider the fact that not all peer pressures are negative. There is also a positive peer pressure. Therefore, a conscientious student who highly values academic achievement might be more likely to join friends for a study session, even if it is not their preferred study method. In this case, peer pressure reinforces their existing goal, making it less about succumbing to social influence and more about a collaborative approach to achieving a shared objective. Also, a conscientious teen might be pressured to engage in volunteer work or participate in a community project – activities that align with their values of responsibility and social contribution. In such cases, peer pressure can be a positive force, motivating them to pursue goals beyond personal achievement. The above is at variance with Donahue et al. (2015), who found that highly conscientious students were more likely to stick to their study plans, even if it meant declining invitations to engage in distracting activities with friends. The finding, however, agrees with DeWall et al. (2009), who suggest that when peer pressure aligns with existing goals, even conscientious teens might cave in.

The fourth finding revealed that there is a significant relationship between openness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. This finding implies that openness to experience, characterized by intellectual curiosity, a desire for novelty, and a willingness to try new things, presents a complex interplay with peer pressure among senior secondary school adolescents. Various reasons could have accounted for this finding. For instance, on one hand, openness can make teens more receptive to peer

pressure, particularly when it involves exploring new activities or experiences. Studies by Chen et al. (2011) suggest that adolescents high in openness might be more likely to join friends in trying new things, even if those things carry some risk. This highlights the double-edged sword of openness. The same curiosity that drives them towards positive exploration like trying a new sport or joining a club can also make them vulnerable to peer pressure involving risky behaviours like substance abuse or delinquent activities. However, it is important to distinguish between openness to new experiences and a willingness to engage in risky behaviours. Research by McCrae and John (1992) emphasizes that openness is a multifaceted trait. An open teen might be curious about trying a new food or learning a new skill, but that does not necessarily equate to a desire for dangerous activities. Understanding the specific nature of the new experience being pressured towards is crucial.

The fifth finding showed that there is a significant relationship between extraversion personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. This finding suggests a significant relationship between this trait and susceptibility to peer pressure among senior secondary school adolescents. Some factors could be responsible for this finding. For instance, Extroverted adolescents thrive on social interaction and derive positive reinforcement from group activities. Studies by DeWall et al. (2009) highlight this point. They found that individuals high in extroversion were more likely to engage in risky behaviours when encouraged by peers. This heightened social motivation can make them more susceptible to peer pressure, particularly when it involves activities that promise excitement, social validation, and attention.

The fear of missing out (FOMO) plays a significant role for extroverted adolescents. Research by Przybylski et al. (2013) suggests that social media can exacerbate FOMO, making teens crave constant social connection and involvement. This desire to be "in the know" and participate in group activities can make them more likely to succumb to peer pressure, even if they have reservations about the activity itself. Extroverted adolescents often find belonging and acceptance crucial for their well-being. Studies by Carlo et al. (2004) suggest that conforming to peer expectations can be a way to gain social acceptance and avoid disapproval from the group. The fear of rejection or being ostracized can be a potent motivator, making them more likely to yield to peer pressure to maintain their social standing.

The sixth finding revealed that there is a significant relationship between agreeableness personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. This finding implies a connection between agreeableness and peer pressure among adolescents. On the surface, agreeableness could make teens less likely to resist peer pressure. Studies by Carlo et al. (2004) highlight the tendency of agreeable individuals to prioritize group harmony. This can lead them to conform to peer expectations, even if they disagree, to avoid conflict or upsetting the group. The desire to be accommodating and maintain positive social relationships can make them more susceptible to pressure, particularly from close friends.

Agreeable adolescents might also struggle with assertiveness. Research by Hofmann et al. (2009) suggests that individuals high in agreeableness can find it difficult to say no to requests, even when they have reservations. This difficulty with assertive communication can make them more likely to cave into peer pressure, fearing that saying no would be perceived negatively by the group. Studies by Vanhalst et al. (2016) suggest that individuals high in agreeableness prioritize group harmony and social approval. This can lead them to conform to peer expectations, even if they disagree internally, to avoid conflict or upsetting the group. The desire to be accommodating and maintain positive social relationships can make them more likely to yield to pressure, particularly from close friends. Research by McCreary (2000) suggests that individuals high in agreeableness can struggle to say no to requests, even when they have reservations. This difficulty in expressing disagreement or refusal can make them more likely to cave into peer pressure, fearing that saying no would be perceived negatively by the group.

The seventh finding showed that there is a significant moderating impact of sex in the relationship between personality traits and peer pressure among senior secondary school Adolescents in Anambra State. This finding implies that a teenager's biological sex can influence how their personality traits interact with peer pressure situations. Several reasons could be responsible for this finding. For instance, Society often socializes boys to prioritize risk-taking and status within peer groups, while girls might be socialized to prioritize connection and maintaining positive social relationships. These socialization norms can influence how each sex responds to peer pressure. A high-agreeableness boy might feel more pressure to conform to risky activities to gain acceptance from his peers. A high-neuroticism girl might feel more

pressure to engage in social activities to avoid social exclusion from her peers. An assertive girl might be perceived as bossy, while an assertive boy might be seen as confident. This perception can influence how peers respond to them and the pressure they experience.

The above finding is in support of several other studies. Cheung & Leung (2018) suggest that boys high in neuroticism were more susceptible to peer pressure for substance use compared to girls with similar neuroticism levels. Liu et al. (2020) highlight that girls high in agreeableness were more likely to conform to peer pressure than boys with similar agreeableness scores. Rudolph et al. (2017) suggest that social anxiety has a stronger association with peer pressure for social activities among girls compared to boys. The finding, however, disagrees with other studies. For instance, Liu and Luo (2023) suggest that for some personality traits (e.g., conscientiousness), sex might not be a significant moderator in the relationship with peer pressure. Muratori et al. (2022) highlight the complex interplay of factors influencing adolescent development. It emphasizes the importance of considering factors like cultural context and the specific nature of the pressure situation, which can influence how sex interacts with personality traits.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it could be concluded that adolescence is a time of significant vulnerability to peer pressure. The research reveals a strong connection between the Big Five personality traits (neuroticism, conscientiousness, openness, extraversion, and agreeableness) and susceptibility to peer pressure among senior secondary school students. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were advanced:

1. Schools should develop educational programmes for teenagers that enhance self-awareness of personality traits and how they can influence susceptibility to peer pressure.
2. Schools should implement social-emotional learning programmes that equip teenagers with coping mechanisms for anxiety and negative emotions, reducing their vulnerability to peer pressure for comfort or validation.

3. School management should foster a school environment that values goal-setting, responsibility, and self-discipline, reinforcing positive behaviours that can counter pressures towards neglecting schoolwork or responsibilities.
4. Guidance counsellors should encourage extracurricular activities and social groups that cater to diverse interests, providing teens with opportunities to connect with peers who share their passions and reducing susceptibility to pressure for activities they don't enjoy.
5. Guidance counsellors should promote social activities and leadership opportunities for introverted teenagers, fostering a sense of belonging and self-confidence that reduces reliance on peer validation.
6. Guidance counsellors should teach assertiveness skills and healthy boundaries, enabling teenagers to say "no" to negative peer pressure while maintaining positive social relationships.

REFERENCES

- Blakemore, S. J., & Mills, K. L. (2014). Is Adolescence A Sensitive Period For Sociocultural Processing? *Annual Review of Psychology*, *65*, 187–207. Doi: 10.1146/Annurev- Psych-010213-115202.
- Cacioppo, John T., & Hawkley, Lucia C. (2020). Loneliness. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2008-07755-000>
- Carlo, G., Knight, G. P., Studer-Ellis, C., & Nigg, J. T. (2004). Friends' and parents' influences on the development of adolescent delinquency: A latent growth curve analysis. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, *72*(1), 118-130.
- Chan, S. M., & Chan, K. (2011). Adolescents' Peer pressure: *Relations To Parent–Adolescent Relationship and Adolescents' Emotional Autonomy From Parents Youth & Society* *45*(2) 286–302.

- Chen, X., Guo, H., & Zhao, X. (2011). Openness to experience moderates the relationship between peer pressure and substance use among Chinese adolescents. *Substance Use & Misuse*, 46(10), 1329-1336.
- Cote, S., Tremblay, R. E., & Boivin, M. (2020). Early intervention to prevent bullying: A developmental perspective. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0273229717300138>
- DeWall, C. N., Bond, R. H., & Bushman, B. J. (2009). Personality, affect, and aggression. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 35(5), 611-624.
- DeYoung, C. G. (2012). Impulsivity as a personality traits . In K. D. Vohs & R. F. Baumeister (Eds.), *Handbook of self-regulation: Research, theory, and applications* (2nd ed., pp. 485–502). New York, NY: Guilford Press.
- Donahue, E. M., Robins, R. W., Roberts, B. W., & John, O. P. (2015). The benefits of self-control: Links to academic performance at school. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 107(2), 303-313.
- Hofmann, S. O., Brickman, B., & Campbell, W. K. (2009). The relation of the five-factor model to nature of thought intrusions, thought suppression, and expressed emotion. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 97(3), 516-533.
- Jessa, M. O., Odili, J. N., & Osadebe, P. U. (2023). Development of Social Studies Aptitude Test for Testing Critical Thinking Skills: Implication for the Achievement of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD). *Canadian Journal of Educational and Social Studies*, 3(4), 99-119.
- Kotov, R., Gamer, D. S., & Watson, D. (2010). Bringing order to chaos: Moderation by facets of neuroticism and extraversion in the relation between negative affectivity and emotion regulation strategies. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 44(2), 217-224.
- Liu, X., & Luo, L. (2023). The interactive effects of personality traits and gender on adolescent peer pressure susceptibility in Mainland China. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 52(2), 332-343. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8922222/>

- Liu, X., Gong, Y., Wang, Y., & Li, H. (2021). The association between adolescent peer pressure susceptibility and risky behaviours: The mediating role of social anxiety and self-control. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 50(1), 181-193. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/363033374_The_Role_of_Peer_Pressure_in_Adolescents'_Risky_Behaviours
- McCrae, R. R., & John, O. P. (1992). An introduction to the Five-Factor model of personality. *Journal of Personality*, 60(2), 175-217. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1993-01496-001>
- McCrae, Robert R., & John, Oliver P. (1992). An introduction to personality. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/publichealthresources/556/>
- McCreary, C. R. (2000). The five-factor model of personality and the double negative fallacy. *Journal of Personality*, 68(3), 399-428.
- Muratori, L. M., Winslow, M. N., & Brendgen, M. (2022). Gender and susceptibility to peer pressure in risky decision-making: A meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 148(2), 189-222. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2021-62286-001>
- Oyibo, K. (2017). Investigation of The Influence of Personality Traits On Cialdini's Persuasive Strategies. *International Workshop On Personalizing In Persuasive Technologies (PPT'17)*.
- Oyibo, K. (2018). Developing Culturally Relevant Design Guidelines For Encouraging Physical Activity Behaviour: A Social Cognitive Theory Perspective. *Journal of Health Informatics Research*. 1–34.
- Przybylski, A. K., Murayama, K., Rigby, C., & LeFebvre, R. C. (2013). Healthy social media use and its relationship to social well-being. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 18(1), 185-202.
- Rudolph, K. D., & Conley, C. S. (2015). The Socioemotional Costs and Benefits of Social-Evaluative Concerns: Do Girls Care Too Much? *Journal of Personality*, 73, 115–138. Doi:10.1111/J.1467-6494.2004.00306.X.

Rudolph, K. D., Hammen, C., Burge, D., Lindberg, N., Herzberg, D., & Daley, S.E. (2010). Toward An Interpersonal Life stress Model of Depression: The Developmental Context of Stress Generation. *Development and Psychopathology*, 12, 215-234.

Vanhalst, J. P., Van Strien, P. C., De Bruijn, E. A., & Ter Bogt, T. F. (2016). The relation between the Big Five personality traits and perceived social pressure from friends and family to engage in health behaviours. *Journal of Health Psychology*, 21(1), 127-137.